

**LECTURE HALL PARTITIONS AND
THE WREATH PRODUCTS $C_k \wr S_n$**

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Abstract

It is shown that statistics on the wreath product groups, $C_k \wr S_n$, can be interpreted in terms of natural statistics on lecture hall partitions. Lecture hall theory is applied to prove distribution results for statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$. Finally, some new statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ are introduced, inspired by lecture hall theory, and their distributions are derived.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this note is to show that statistics on the wreath product $C_k \wr S_n$ of a cyclic group C_k , of order k , and the symmetric group S_n , can be interpreted in terms of natural statistics on lecture hall partitions. We demonstrate that lecture hall theory can be used to prove results about the distribution of statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$. We introduce some new statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$, inspired by lecture hall partitions, including a quadratic version of “flag-major index”, and prove distribution results for these statistics.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we define the \mathbf{s} -lecture hall partitions and state a few useful results. Section 3 is devoted to statistics of interest on the wreath product groups and a very brief discussion of what is known. Section 4 introduces \mathbf{s} -inversion sequences, which will be used to relate statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ to statistics on lecture hall partitions.

Section 5 describes a bijection between $(k, 2k, \dots, nk)$ -inversion sequences and

$C_k \wr S_n$ that allows statistics to be translated from one domain to another.

Section 6 reviews recent work of Savage-Schuster [13] relating inversion sequences to lecture hall partitions. This work was developed with the intention of extending work on permutation statistics to a more general setting.

Section 7 is the heart of the paper. We prove there a theorem which allows us to apply the tools of Section 6 to $C_k \wr S_n$. This contains our main results relating statistics such as descent, flag-major index and flag-inversion number to statistics on lecture hall partitions, also proving an Euler-Mahonian distribution result.

In Section 8 we define a new statistic “lhall” on $C_k \wr S_n$ and derive its surprisingly nice distribution.

In Section 9, we are led to define a distorted version of the descent statistic on $C_k \wr S_n$, that reveals an even closer connection to lecture hall partitions.

A few words about notation: \mathbb{Z} is the set of integers, \mathbb{R} the set of real numbers, S_n the set of permutations of n elements; $[j] = \{1, 2, \dots, j\}$, where $[0] = \emptyset$; $[n]_q = (1 - q^n)/(1 - q)$; and for $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, $|x| = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$.

2. Lecture Hall Partitions

For a sequence $\mathbf{s} = \{s_i\}_{i \geq 1}$ of positive integers, the \mathbf{s} -lecture hall partitions are the elements of the set

$$\mathbf{L}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} = \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbb{Z}^n \mid 0 \leq \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \leq \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \leq \dots \leq \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \right\}.$$

For example, $(0, 1, 3, 4) \in \mathbf{L}_n^{(1,2,3,4)}$, but $(0, 1, 3, 4) \notin \mathbf{L}_n^{(1,3,5,7)}$, since $3/5 > 4/7$.

The original lecture hall partitions $\mathbf{L}_n = \mathbf{L}_n^{(1,2,\dots,n)}$ were introduced by Bousquet-Mélou and Eriksson in [3], where they showed that

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} y^{|\lambda|} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{1 - y^{2i-1}}. \tag{1}$$

In [4] they proved the following refinement, which will be useful in the present work.

Theorem 1. The Refined Lecture Hall Theorem [4]: *For any nonnegative integer n ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil|} y^{|\lambda|} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1 + qy^i}{1 - q^2 y^{n+i}}, \tag{2}$$

where $\lceil \lambda \rceil = (\lceil \lambda_1/1 \rceil, \lceil \lambda_2/2 \rceil, \dots, \lceil \lambda_n/n \rceil)$.

If the largest part in a lecture hall partition in \mathbf{L}_n is constrained, we have the following.

Theorem 2. [8, 13] For integers $n \geq 1$ and $t \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n; \lambda_n \leq tn} q^{|\lambda|} = [t+1]_q^n. \tag{3}$$

For example, when $n = 3$ and $t = 1$, the set $\{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_3 \mid \lambda_3 \leq 3\}$ has the eight elements:

$$\{(0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 1), (0, 0, 2), (0, 0, 3), (0, 1, 2), (0, 1, 3), (0, 2, 3), (1, 2, 3)\}$$

and

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_3; \lambda_3 \leq 3} q^{[\lambda_1/1] + [\lambda_2/2] + [\lambda_3/3]} = 1 + 3q + 3q^2 + q^3 = [2]_q^3.$$

3. Statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$

An element $\pi \in S_n$ is a bijection $\pi : [n] \rightarrow [n]$ and we write $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$, to mean that $\pi(i) = \pi_i$. A *descent* in $\pi \in S_n$ is a position $i \in [n-1]$ such that $\pi_i > \pi_{i+1}$. The set of all descents of π is $\text{Des } \pi$ and $\text{des } \pi = |\text{Des } \pi|$. The *inversion* number of π is

$$\text{inv } \pi = |\{(i, j) \mid 1 \leq i < j \leq n \text{ and } \pi_i > \pi_j\}|.$$

For example, if $\pi = (5, 4, 1, 3, 2)$, then $\text{Des } \pi = \{1, 2, 4\}$, $\text{des } \pi = 3$ and $\text{inv } \pi = 8$.

For positive integers k and n , we view $C_k \wr S_n$ combinatorially as a set of pairs (π, σ) :

$$C_k \wr S_n = \{(\pi, \sigma) \mid \pi \in S_n, \sigma \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}^n\}.$$

We use the notation π^σ to denote (π, σ) and write

$$\pi^\sigma = (\pi_1^{\sigma_1}, \pi_2^{\sigma_2}, \dots, \pi_n^{\sigma_n}) = ((\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n), (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n)) = (\pi, \sigma).$$

Statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ (or k -colored permutations or k -indexed permutations) have been studied by many, starting with Reiner’s work on signed permutations [12], followed by independent work of Brenti [5] and Steingrímsson [14] on the more general wreath products. Pairs of “(descent, major index)” statistics have been found, satisfying relations like Carlitz’s q -Eulerian polynomials, starting with work of Adin, Brenti, and Roichman [1]. There have very recently been many new and exciting discoveries, including [7, 10, 9, 2]. It is remarkable the many variations in the definitions of the statistics, even when they give the same distribution.

We start with a fairly standard definition of *descent*. The *descent set* of $\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n$ is

$$\text{Des } \pi^\sigma = \{i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \mid \sigma_i < \sigma_{i+1}, \text{ or } \sigma_i = \sigma_{i+1} \text{ and } \pi_i > \pi_{i+1}\}, \tag{4}$$

with the convention that $\pi_0 = \sigma_0 = 0$.

We will consider the following statistics defined on $C_k \wr S_n$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{des } \pi^\sigma &= |\text{Des } \pi^\sigma| \\ \text{comaj } \pi^\sigma &= \sum_{i \in \text{Des } \pi^\sigma} (n - i) \\ \text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma &= k \text{comaj } \pi^\sigma - \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i \\ \text{finv } \pi^\sigma &= \text{inv } \pi + \sum_{i=1}^n i\sigma_i. \end{aligned}$$

As an example, for $\pi^\sigma = (5^1, 4^1, 1^0, 3^0, 2^2) \in C_3 \wr S_5$, we have $\text{Des } \pi^\sigma = \{0, 1, 4\}$; $\text{des } \pi^\sigma = 3$; $\text{comaj } \pi^\sigma = 10$; $\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma = 26$; and $\text{finv } \pi^\sigma = 21$. Note that this definition of fmaj differs a bit from those appearing elsewhere, even among those who define the descent set as in (4) ([1, 7]).

Using lecture hall theory, we will show, among other things:

$$\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} = \sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{finv } \pi^\sigma}, \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} [kt + 1]_q^n x^t = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{\text{des } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{ki})}, \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|} x^{[\lambda_n/(kn)]} = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{\text{des } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - xq^{ki})}. \tag{7}$$

Relations of the form (6), for general k , have been found only recently, starting with Chow and Mansour [7] and Hyatt [10], sometimes with slightly different definitions of Des or fmaj . Our intention here is to highlight our methods, which are quite novel, and which allow us to prove new results like (7).

4. Statistics on s-Inversion Sequences

The connection between statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ and statistics on lecture hall partitions will be made via statistics on *inversion sequences*.

Given a sequence $\mathbf{s} = \{s_i\}_{i \geq 1}$ of positive integers, and positive integer n , the set $\mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ of *s-inversion sequences* is defined by

$$\mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} = \{(e_1, \dots, e_n) \in \mathbb{Z}^n \mid 0 \leq e_i < s_i \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n\}.$$

The familiar “inversion sequences” associated with permutations are the elements of $\mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ for $\mathbf{s} = (1, 2, \dots, n)$.

The *ascent set* of an inversion sequence $e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ is the set

$$\text{Asc } e = \left\{ i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \mid \frac{e_i}{s_i} < \frac{e_{i+1}}{s_{i+1}} \right\},$$

with the convention that $e_0 = 0$. For example, as an element of $\mathbf{I}_5^{(3,6,9,12,15)}$, the inversion sequence $e = (1, 3, 2, 2, 13)$ has the ascent set $\text{Asc } e = \{0, 1, 4\}$.

The following statistics on $\mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ were defined in [13]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{asc } e &= |\text{Asc } e|, \\ \text{amaj } e &= \sum_{i \in \text{Asc } e} (n - i), \\ |e| &= \sum_{i=1}^n e_i, \\ \text{lhpe} &= -|e| + \sum_{i \in \text{Asc } e} (s_{i+1} + \dots + s_n). \end{aligned}$$

For $e = (1, 3, 2, 2, 13) \in \mathbf{I}_5^{(3,6,9,12,15)}$, we have $\text{asc } e = 3$; $\text{amaj } e = 10$; $|e| = 21$; and $\text{lhpe} = 81$.

In this paper, our focus is the sequence $\mathbf{s} = (k, 2k, \dots, nk)$, where k is a positive integer. Let $\mathbf{I}_{n,k} = \mathbf{I}_n^{(k,2k,\dots,nk)}$. We will require two new statistics on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{N}(e) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \left\lfloor \frac{e_j}{j} \right\rfloor; \\ \text{Ifmaj } e &= k \text{ amaj } e - \mathbf{N}(e). \end{aligned}$$

For $e = (1, 3, 2, 2, 13) \in \mathbf{I}_5^{(3,6,9,12,15)}$, $\mathbf{N}(e) = 4$ and $\text{Ifmaj } e = 26$.

5. From Statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ to Statistics on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$

We will make use of the following bijection between S_n and $\mathbf{I}_{n,1}$ which was proved in [13] to have the required properties.

Lemma 1. *For positive integer n , the mapping $\phi : S_n \rightarrow \mathbf{I}_{n,1}$ defined by $\phi(\pi) = t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$, where*

$$t_i = |\{j \in [i-1] \mid \pi_j > \pi_i\}|$$

is a bijection satisfying both $\text{Des } \pi = \text{Asc } t$ and $\text{inv } \pi = |t|$.

For example, if $\pi = (5, 4, 1, 3, 2)$ then $t = \phi(\pi) = (0, 1, 2, 2, 3) \in \mathbf{I}_{5,1}$. Checking the statistics, $\text{Des } \pi = \{1, 2, 4\} = \text{Asc } t$ and $\text{inv } \pi = 8 = |t|$.

Noting that, as sets, $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$ and $C_k \wr S_n$ have the same cardinality, we set up a bijection which translates statistics from one domain to the other in a useful way.

Theorem 3. *For each pair of integers (n, k) with $n \geq 1, k \geq 1$, there is a bijection*

$$\Theta : C_k \wr S_n \longrightarrow \mathbf{I}_{n,k}$$

with the following properties. If $\Theta(\pi^\sigma) = e = (e_1, \dots, e_n)$ then

$$\text{Asc } e = \text{Des } \pi^\sigma \tag{8}$$

$$N(e) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i \tag{9}$$

$$\text{Ifmaj } e = \text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma \tag{10}$$

$$e_n = n(\sigma_n + 1) - \pi_n \tag{11}$$

$$|e| = \text{inv } \pi + \sum_{i=1}^n i\sigma_i = \text{finv } \pi^\sigma. \tag{12}$$

Proof. Define Θ by

$$e = \Theta(\pi_1^{\sigma_1}, \pi_2^{\sigma_2}, \dots, \pi_n^{\sigma_n}) = (\sigma_1 + t_1, 2\sigma_2 + t_2, \dots, n\sigma_n + t_n),$$

where $(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n) = \phi(\pi)$, as in Lemma 1.

For example, for $\pi^\sigma = (5^1, 4^1, 1^0, 3^0, 2^2) \in C_3 \wr S_5, t = \phi(5, 4, 1, 3, 2) = (0, 1, 2, 2, 3)$, so we get $e = \Theta(\pi^\sigma) = (1, 3, 2, 2, 13)$. Note that properties (8) through (12) hold for this example:

$$\text{Asc } e = \{0, 1, 4\} = \text{Des } \pi^\sigma$$

$$N(e) = 4 = 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 4 = |\sigma|$$

$$\text{Ifmaj } e = 26 = \text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma$$

$$e_5 = 13 = 5(\sigma_5 + 1) - \pi_5$$

$$|e| = 21 = \text{finv } \pi^\sigma.$$

Clearly, $\Theta(\pi^\sigma) \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}$. Since $C_k \wr S_n$ and $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$ have the same cardinality, to show that Θ is a bijection, it suffices to show that Θ is onto. Let $e = (e_1, \dots, e_n) \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}$. Define $\sigma = (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n)$ by $\sigma_i = \lfloor e_i/i \rfloor$. Then $\sigma \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}^n$. Define $t = (t_1, \dots, t_n)$ by $t_i = e_i - i\sigma_i$. Then $t \in \mathbf{I}_{n,1}$. Finally, let $\pi = \phi^{-1}(t) \in S_n$. Then $\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n$ and $\Theta^{-1}(e) = \pi^\sigma$.

To prove properties (8) through (12), observe first that $t_n = n - \pi_n$, so property (11) holds. It is clear from the definition of Θ that (12) is true. Also, note that $\lfloor e_i/i \rfloor = \sigma_i$ since $0 \leq t_i < i$ and property (9) holds. So property (10) will follow

once we prove (8). By Lemma 1, since $t = \phi(\pi)$, we know that $\text{Asc } t = \text{Des } \pi$, so it remains to show $\text{Asc } e = \text{Des } \pi^\sigma$.

Note first that $e_1 = \sigma_1 + t_1 = \sigma_1$, since $t_1 = 0$. So,

$$0 \in \text{Des } \pi^\sigma \iff \sigma_1 > 0 \iff e_1 > 0 \iff 0 \in \text{Asc } e.$$

For $1 \leq i \leq n$, $i \in \text{Asc } e$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < \frac{e_{i+1}}{k(i+1)} - \frac{e_i}{ki} &= \frac{(i+1)\sigma_{i+1} + t_{i+1}}{k(i+1)} - \frac{i\sigma_i + t_i}{ki} \\ &= \frac{i(i+1)(\sigma_{i+1} - \sigma_i) + it_{i+1} - (i+1)t_i}{ki(i+1)} \\ &= \frac{\Delta_i}{ki(i+1)}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Delta_i = i(i+1)(\sigma_{i+1} - \sigma_i) + it_{i+1} - (i+1)t_i.$$

So, $i \in \text{Asc } e$ if and only if $\Delta_i > 0$.

If $\sigma_i = \sigma_{i+1}$ then

$$\Delta_i > 0 \iff it_{i+1} - (i+1)t_i > 0 \iff i \in \text{Asc } t \iff i \in \text{Des } \pi \iff i \in \text{Des } \pi^\sigma.$$

For the remaining cases, note that since $0 \leq t_{i+1} \leq i$ and $0 \leq t_i \leq i-1$,

$$i(i+1)(\sigma_{i+1} - \sigma_i) - i^2 + 1 \leq \Delta_i \leq i(i+1)(\sigma_{i+1} - \sigma_i) + i^2.$$

If $\sigma_i \neq \sigma_{i+1}$, then $i \in \text{Des } \pi^\sigma$ if and only if $\sigma_i < \sigma_{i+1}$. But if $\sigma_i < \sigma_{i+1}$, then

$$\Delta_i \geq i(i+1) - i^2 + 1 = i+1 > 0,$$

so $i \in \text{Asc } e$. And if $\sigma_i > \sigma_{i+1}$ then

$$\Delta_i \leq -i(i+1) + i^2 = -i \leq 0$$

and $i \notin \text{Asc } e$. This completes the proof. □

6. Lecture Hall Polytopes and s-Inversion Sequences

The *s-lecture hall polytope* was introduced in [13], for an arbitrary sequence $\mathbf{s} = \{s_i\}_{i \geq 1}$ of positive integers, as

$$\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} = \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid 0 \leq \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \leq \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \leq \dots \leq \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

$\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ is a convex, simplicial polytope with the $n + 1$ vertices:

$$(0, 0, \dots, 0), (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n), (0, s_2, \dots, s_n), (0, 0, s_3, \dots, s_n), \dots, (0, 0, \dots, 0, s_n),$$

all with integer coordinates. The t -th *dilation* of $\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ is the polytope

$$t\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} = \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid 0 \leq \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \leq \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \leq \dots \leq \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \leq t \right\}.$$

A multivariate function, $\mathbf{f}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}(t; q, y, z)$, was used in [13] to enumerate lattice points in $t\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ according to statistics significant in the theory of lecture hall partitions:

$$\mathbf{f}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}(t; q, y, z) = \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{P}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil_{\mathbf{s}}|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon^+(\lambda)|},$$

where

$$\lceil \lambda \rceil_{\mathbf{s}} = \left(\left\lceil \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \right\rceil, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \right\rceil, \dots, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \right\rceil \right), \tag{13}$$

$$\epsilon^+(\lambda) = \left(s_1 \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \right\rceil - \lambda_1, s_2 \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \right\rceil - \lambda_2, \dots, s_n \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \right\rceil - \lambda_n \right). \tag{14}$$

The following theorems show the connection between statistics on \mathbf{s} -inversion sequences and statistics on \mathbf{s} -lecture hall partitions.

Theorem 4. ([13]) *For any sequence \mathbf{s} of positive integers, and any positive integer n ,*

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \mathbf{f}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}(t; q, y, z) x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{n-i} y^{s_{i+1} + \dots + s_n})}. \tag{15}$$

Theorem 5. ([13]) *For any sequence \mathbf{s} of positive integers, and any positive integer n ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil_{\mathbf{s}}|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon^+(\lambda)|} x^{\lceil \lambda_n / s_n \rceil} = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - xq^{n-i} y^{s_{i+1} + \dots + s_n})}. \tag{16}$$

7. Lecture Hall Partitions and the Inversion Sequences $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$

In order to apply the results of the previous section to the problem of interest, we need an analog of Ifmaj on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$ for lecture hall partitions.

First observe that the following sets of lecture hall partitions are all the same:

$$\mathbf{L}_n = \mathbf{L}_n^{(1,2,\dots,n)} = \mathbf{L}_n^{(2,4,\dots,2n)} = \mathbf{L}_n^{(3,6,\dots,3n)} = \dots$$

However, the lecture hall polytopes $\mathbf{P}_{n,k}$ defined by

$$\mathbf{P}_{n,k} = \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid 0 \leq \frac{\lambda_1}{k} \leq \frac{\lambda_2}{2k} \leq \dots \leq \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \leq 1 \right\}$$

are different for different k . On the other hand, the following dilations *are* the same

$$t\mathbf{P}_{n,k} = kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1}, \tag{17}$$

a fact we will exploit. Furthermore,

$$kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n = \{ \lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n \mid \lambda_n \leq ktn \}.$$

Since the definitions (13) and (14) depend on the sequence $\mathbf{s} = (k, 2k, \dots, nk)$, we will make the dependence explicit in the notation. For $\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n$ and $k \geq 1$, let:

$$\lceil \lambda \rceil_k = \left(\left\lceil \frac{\lambda_1}{k} \right\rceil, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_2}{2k} \right\rceil, \dots, \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \right\rceil \right); \tag{18}$$

$$\epsilon_k^+(\lambda) = \left(k \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_1}{k} \right\rceil - \lambda_1, 2k \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_2}{2k} \right\rceil - \lambda_2, \dots, nk \left\lceil \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \right\rceil - \lambda_n \right); \tag{19}$$

$$\eta_k(\lambda) = k \lceil \lambda \rceil_k - \lceil \lambda \rceil. \tag{20}$$

Note: for $\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n$,

$$\lceil \lambda \rceil_1 = \lceil \lambda \rceil,$$

where $\lceil \lambda \rceil$ was defined in Theorem 1.

We now show that the new statistic η_k on \mathbf{L}_n corresponds to the statistic \mathbf{N} on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$.

Theorem 6. *For positive integers n, k , let*

$$\mathbf{f}_{n,k}(t; q, y, z, w) = \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{P}_{n,k} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil_k|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} w^{|\eta_k(\lambda)|}. \tag{21}$$

Then

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \mathbf{f}_{n,k}(t; q, y, z, w) x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|} w^{\mathbf{N}(e)}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{n-i} y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1)/2})}. \tag{22}$$

Proof. If $w = 1$, this is just the case $\mathbf{s} = (k, 2k, \dots, nk)$ of Theorem 4. To include w , we appeal to the combinatorial proof of (15) in Theorem 4 that was presented

in [13]. In that proof, $\lambda \in (t\mathbf{P}_{n,k} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n)$ is associated with the inversion sequence $\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)$, which, by definition, is in $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$. It suffices to check that $|\eta_k(\lambda)| = \mathbf{N}(\epsilon_k^+(\lambda))$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{N}(\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left\lfloor \frac{ik \lceil \lambda_i / (ik) \rceil - \lambda_i}{i} \right\rfloor \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n [k \lceil \lambda_i / (ik) \rceil - \lambda_i / i] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n (k \lceil \lambda_i / (ik) \rceil - \lceil \lambda_i / i \rceil) \\ &= |k \lceil \lambda \rceil_k - \lceil \lambda \rceil_1| = |\eta_k(\lambda)|. \end{aligned}$$

□

The Ifmaj statistic is obtained by setting $q = q^k$ and $w = q^{-1}$ in Theorem 6.

Corollary 1. For positive integers n, k ,

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \sum_{\lambda \in kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } z|e|}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{k(n-i)} y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})} \tag{23}$$

Proof. With $q = q^k$ and $w = q^{-1}$, the numerator in the right-hand side of (22) becomes

$$x^{\text{asc } e} q^{k \text{ amaj } e - \mathbf{N}(e)} y^{\text{lhpe } z|e|} = x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } z|e|}.$$

From (21), the left-hand side summand of (22) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_{n,k}(t; q^k, y, z, q^{-1}) &= \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{P}_{n,k} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{k|\lceil \lambda \rceil_k| - |\eta_k(\lambda)|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} \\ &= \sum_{\lambda \in kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} \end{aligned}$$

by (18)-(20) and by (17). □

Corollary 2. For positive integers n, k ,

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lceil \lambda \rceil|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} x^{\lceil \lambda_n / (nk) \rceil} = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } z|e|}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - xq^{k(n-i)} y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})}. \tag{24}$$

Proof. For $t > 0$, let $H(t) = \sum_{\lambda \in kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|_1} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|}$ from (23), with $H(0) = 1$. Then for $t > 0$, since

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n; \left\lfloor \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \right\rfloor = t \right\} &= \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n; \left\lfloor \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \right\rfloor \leq t \right\} - \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n; \left\lfloor \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \right\rfloor \leq t-1 \right\} \\ &= (kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n) - (k(t-1)\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n), \end{aligned}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|_1} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} x^{\lfloor \lambda_n / (nk) \rfloor} &= \sum_{t \geq 0} x^t \sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n; \lfloor \frac{\lambda_n}{nk} \rfloor = t} q^{|\lambda|_1} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{t \geq 1} (H(t) - H(t-1))x^t \\ &= 1 + \sum_{t \geq 1} H(t)x^t - \sum_{t \geq 1} H(t-1)x^t \\ &= \sum_{t \geq 0} H(t)x^t - x \sum_{t \geq 0} H(t)x^t \\ &= (1-x) \sum_{t \geq 0} H(t)x^t. \end{aligned}$$

But $\sum_{t \geq 0} H(t)x^t$ is the left-hand side of (23), so we simply multiply the right-hand side of (23) by $(1-x)$ to complete the proof. \square

We can now apply these results to the wreath product groups. First, we have the expected result that the pair $(\text{des}, \text{fmaj})$ is Euler-Mahonian.

Theorem 7. *For positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} [kt + 1]_q^n x^t = \frac{\sum_{\pi \sigma \in C_{k\ell} S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi \sigma} x^{\text{des } \pi \sigma}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{ki})}.$$

Proof. Set $y = z = 1$ in (23). On the left-hand side, in the summand, we get

$$\sum_{\lambda \in kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|_1}.$$

Since $kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n = \{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n \mid \lambda_n \leq ktn\}$, by Theorem 2,

$$\sum_{\lambda \in kt\mathbf{P}_{n,1} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|_1} = [kt + 1]_q^n.$$

For the right-hand side, we get

$$\frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{asc } e} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - xq^{k(n-i)})}.$$

Reindex the product in the denominator and for the numerator, use the fact that by Theorem 3, the distribution of $(\text{des}, \text{fmaj})$ on $C_k \wr S_n$ is the same as the distribution of $(\text{asc}, \text{Ifmaj})$ on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$. \square

Now, to interpret the distribution $(\text{des}, \text{fmaj}, \text{finv})$ on $C_k \wr S_n$ in terms of lecture hall partitions, set $y = 1$ in (24) and use Theorem 3.

Theorem 8. *For positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} x^{\lceil \lambda_n / (nk) \rceil} = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{\text{des } \pi^\sigma} z^{\text{finv } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - xq^{ki})}.$$

The implication of Theorem 8 for $z = 1$ is quite interesting. We have

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|} x^{\lceil \lambda_n / (nk) \rceil} = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{\text{des } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - xq^{ki})}. \tag{25}$$

In the left-hand side of (25), the only dependence on k is in the exponent of x , in a statistic involving only the last part of λ . We take this further in Section 9.

8. A Lecture Hall Statistic on $C_k \wr S_n$

From the point of view of partition theory, the most important statistic for a lecture hall partition λ is the number $|\lambda| = \lambda_1 + \dots + \lambda_n$ being partitioned. So, what does $|\lambda|$ correspond to on $C_k \wr S_n$?

In [6], a quadratic version of the major index was defined on S_n by $\text{bin } \pi = \sum_{i \in \text{Des } \pi} \binom{i+1}{2}$. In that spirit, we define “cobin” on $C_k \wr S_n$ by

$$\text{cobin } \pi^\sigma = \sum_{i \in \text{Des } \pi^\sigma} \left(\binom{n+1}{2} - \binom{i+1}{2} \right).$$

Now define the statistic “lhall” on $C_k \wr S_n$ by

$$\text{lhall } \pi^\sigma = k \text{cobin } \pi^\sigma - \text{finv } \pi^\sigma.$$

Observe that under the bijection Θ of Theorem 3, if $e = \Theta(\pi^\sigma)$ then $\text{lhall } \pi^\sigma = \text{lhpe}$.

This can be seen as follows, since $|e| = \text{finv } \pi^\sigma$ and $\text{Asc } e = \text{Des } e$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lhpe} &= -|e| + \sum_{i \in \text{Asc } e} (k(i+1) + \dots + kn) \\ &= -|e| + k \sum_{i \in \text{Asc } e} \left(\binom{n+1}{2} - \binom{i+1}{2} \right) \\ &= -\text{finv } \pi^\sigma + k \sum_{i \in \text{Des } e} \left(\binom{n+1}{2} - \binom{i+1}{2} \right) \\ &= -\text{finv } \pi^\sigma + k \text{cobin } \pi^\sigma \\ &= \text{llhall } \pi^\sigma. \end{aligned}$$

The joint distribution of $(\text{llhall}, \text{fmaj})$ on $C_k \wr S_n$ has the following form.

Theorem 9. For positive integers n, k ,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} y^{\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} &= \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(1 + qy^i)(1 - q^{k(n+1-i)}y^{k(i+\dots+n)})}{1 - q^2y^{n+i}} \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} [k(2i-1)]_{qy^{n+1-i}} \prod_{i=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} ([2]_{qy^i} [ki]_{q^2y^{2(n-i)+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Under the bijection Θ of Theorem 3, if $e = \Theta(\pi^\sigma)$ then $\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma = \text{lhpe}$ and $\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma = \text{Ifmaj } e$. So,

$$\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} y^{\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} = \sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} y^{\text{lhpe}} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}.$$

So, by Corollary 2 with $x = z = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} y^{\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{k(n-i)}y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})} &= \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} y^{\text{lhpe}} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{k(n-i)}y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})} \\ &= \sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} y^{|\lambda|} q^{|\lambda|}. \end{aligned}$$

Now apply Theorem 1 to get

$$\frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} y^{\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{k(n-i)}y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1 + qy^i}{1 - q^2y^{n+i}}.$$

So,

$$\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} y^{\text{llhall } \pi^\sigma} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} = \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - q^{k(n-i+1)}y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2}) \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1 + qy^i}{1 - q^2y^{n+i}},$$

which, after simplification, gives the theorem. \square

Setting $y = 1$ in Theorem 9 and simplifying, we get

$$\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} = \prod_{i=1}^n [ki]_q,$$

the same distribution as finv , Ifmaj , and $|e|$, as expected. But the statistic lhall itself also has a surprisingly simple distribution:

Theorem 10. For positive integers n, k ,

$$\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{hall } \pi^\sigma} = \prod_{i=1}^n [ki]_{q^{2(n-i)+1}}.$$

Proof. Set $q = 1$ and $y = q$ in the proof of the Theorem 9, but apply (1) instead of (2) to get:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(1,2,\dots,n)}} q^{\text{hp } e} &= \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1 - q^{k(i+\dots+n)}}{1 - q^{2i-1}} \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \frac{1 - q^{k(2i-1)(n-i+1)}}{1 - q^{2i-1}} \prod_{i=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \frac{1 - q^{ki(2(n-i)+1)}}{1 - q^{2(n-i)+1}} \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^n [ki]_{q^{2(n-i)+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

9. Inflated Eulerian Polynomials for $C_k \wr S_n$

We showed in [11] how to obtain more refined information about the \mathbf{s} -lecture hall partitions by considering the *rational lecture hall polytope* $\mathbf{R}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$:

$$\mathbf{R}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} = \left\{ \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid 0 \leq \frac{\lambda_1}{s_1} \leq \frac{\lambda_2}{s_2} \leq \dots \leq \frac{\lambda_n}{s_n} \text{ and } \lambda_n \leq 1 \right\}.$$

$\mathbf{R}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}$ is a convex simplicial polytope, whose vertices are

$$(0, 0, \dots, 0), \left(\frac{s_1}{s_n}, \frac{s_2}{s_n}, \dots, \frac{s_n}{s_n} \right), \left(0, \frac{s_2}{s_n}, \dots, \frac{s_n}{s_n} \right), \left(0, 0, \frac{s_3}{s_n}, \dots, \frac{s_n}{s_n} \right), \dots, \left(0, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{s_n}{s_n} \right),$$

with rational (but not necessarily integer) coordinates. Let

$$\mathbf{g}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}(t; q, y, z) = \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{R}_n^{(\mathbf{s})} \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} |k y|^{|\lambda|} |z|^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|}. \tag{26}$$

The following theorems were proved in [11]. These are analogs of Theorems 4 and 5.

Theorem 11. ([11]) *For any sequence \mathbf{s} of positive integers, and positive integer n ,*

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \mathbf{g}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}(t; q, y, z) x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|} x^{\text{snasc } e - e_n}}{(1-x) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - x^{s_n} q^{n-i} y^{s_{i+1} + \dots + s_n})}.$$

Theorem 12. ([11]) *For any sequence \mathbf{s} of positive integers, and positive integer n ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} q^{|\lambda|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} x^{\lambda_n} = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_n^{(\mathbf{s})}} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|} x^{\text{snasc } e - e_n}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - x^{s_n} q^{n-i} y^{s_{i+1} + \dots + s_n})}.$$

We can specialize Theorems 11 and 12 to $\mathbf{s} = (k, 2k, \dots, nk)$ and modify to track Ifmaj as in Theorem 6 and its corollaries. We should expect something interesting because

$$\mathbf{R}_n^{(1,2,\dots,n)} = \mathbf{R}_n^{(2,4,\dots,2n)} = \mathbf{R}_n^{(3,6,\dots,3n)} \dots$$

We get the following theorem, which is an analog of Theorem 6. The proof, which is analogous to that of Theorem 6, is omitted.

Theorem 13. *For positive integers n, k , let*

$$\mathbf{g}_{n,k}(t; q, y, z, w) = \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{R}_n \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} y^{|\lambda|} z^{|\epsilon_k^+(\lambda)|} w^{|\eta_k(\lambda)|}. \tag{27}$$

Then

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \mathbf{g}_{n,k}(t; q, y, z, w) x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{knasc } e - e_n} q^{\text{amaj } e} y^{\text{lhpe } e} z^{|e|} w^{\mathbf{N}(e)}}{(1-x) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - x^{kn} q^{n-i} y^{k(n(n+1)-i(i+1))/2})}. \tag{28}$$

The following corollaries of Theorem 13 are analogs of Corollaries 1 and 2 with $y = z = 1$. Note that in the right-hand sides of the equations there is no dependence on k .

Corollary 3. *For positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{R}_n \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} x^t = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{knasc } e - e_n} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}}{(1-x) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - x^{kn} q^{k(n-i)})}.$$

Corollary 4. *For positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|} x^{\lambda_n} = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{\text{knasc } e - e_n} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (1 - x^{kn} q^{k(n-i)})}.$$

Making use of Theorem 3 giving the correspondence between statistics on $\mathbf{I}_{n,k}$ and on $C_k \wr S_n$, we have the following analogs of Theorems 7 and 8. First, We need a result from [8]:

Lemma 2. ([8]) *For integers $t \geq 0$ and $n > 0$, let j and i be the unique integers satisfying $t = jn + i$ where $j \geq 0$ and $0 \leq i < n$. Then*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{R}_n \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} = [j + 1]_q^{n-i} [j + 2]_q^i.$$

Theorem 14. *For positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{j \geq 0} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [j + 1]_q^{n-i} [j + 2]_q^i x^{nj+i} = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{n(k \text{ des } \pi^\sigma - 1 - \sigma_n) + \pi_n}}{(1 - x) \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - x^{kn} q^{ki})}.$$

Proof. By Lemma 2,

$$\sum_{j \geq 0} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [j + 1]_q^{n-i} [j + 2]_q^i x^{nj+i} = \sum_{j \geq 0} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_{\lambda \in (jn+i)\mathbf{R}_n \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} x^{jn+i}.$$

Since every $t \geq 0$ can be written uniquely as $t = jn + i$ for nonnegative integers j and i with $i < n$, the last expression can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{t \geq 0} \sum_{\lambda \in t\mathbf{R}_n \cap \mathbb{Z}^n} q^{|\lambda|} x^t,$$

which, by Corollary 3, is equal to

$$\frac{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{I}_{n,k}} x^{kn \text{ asc } e - e_n} q^{\text{Ifmaj } e}}{\prod_{i=0}^n (1 - x^{kn} q^{k(n-i)})}.$$

Under the bijection Θ of Theorem 3, if $e = \Theta(\pi^\sigma)$ then $\text{Ifmaj } e = \text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma$, $\text{asc } e = \text{des } \pi^\sigma$, and $e_n = n(\sigma_n + 1) - \pi_n$. The result follows then, since

$$kn \text{ asc } e - e_n = kn \text{ des } \pi^\sigma - n(\sigma_n + 1) + \pi_n.$$

□

Theorem 15. *For any positive integers n, k ,*

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbf{L}_n} q^{|\lambda|} x^{\lambda_n} = \frac{\sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} q^{\text{fmaj } \pi^\sigma} x^{n(k \text{ des } \pi^\sigma - 1 - \sigma_n) + \pi_n}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - x^{kn} q^{ki})}.$$

Proof. Start from Corollary 4 and apply Theorem 3.

□

(Note: There is no dependence on k in the left-hand side).

Let $Q_{n,k}(x)$ be the $q = 1$ specialization:

$$Q_{n,k}(x) = \sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} x^{n(k \operatorname{des} \pi^\sigma - 1 - \sigma_n) + \pi_n}.$$

The $Q_{n,k}(x)$ are referred to as *inflated Eulerian polynomials* in [11]. To contrast the usual, Eulerian polynomials for $C_k \wr S_n$ are

$$E_{n,k}(x) = \sum_{\pi^\sigma \in C_k \wr S_n} x^{\operatorname{des} \pi^\sigma}.$$

It is interesting that $Q_{n,k}(x)$ is self-reciprocal, but in general $E_{n,k}(x)$ is not when $k > 2$.

10. Concluding Remarks

It is interesting from the results in Sections 7 - 9 that for fixed n , statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ such as descent, flag-major index, and flag-inversion number appear naturally in the geometry of the *same* simplicial cone, \mathbf{R}_n , independent of k .

It would be interesting to see to what extent other statistics on $C_k \wr S_n$ can be interpreted in terms of lecture hall partitions. Different orderings on $C_k \wr S_n$ and different bijections $C_k \wr S_n \rightarrow \mathbf{I}_{n,k}$ would give different results.

Lecture hall partitions were discovered in the setting of affine Coxeter groups, and Theorem 1 was inspired by Bott's formula. It should be possible to trace through backwards to discover the algebraic significance of the statistic lhall , at least in the Coxeter groups $A_n = C_1 \wr S_n$ or $B_n = C_2 \wr S_n$ but we have not seen how to do this.

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